

Fluorinated phosphonium salts (2a-b): A solution of triphenylphosphine and the appropriate fluoro-phenacyl bromide (0.022 mol) in anhydrous toluene (40 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The resulting phosphonium salt was filtered off, washed with toluene, dried and recrystallised from chloroform-ether.

Fluorinated phosphonium ylides (3a-b): To a stirred suspension of the phosphonium salt (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (50 ml) was added sodium ethoxide (0.05 mol). The mixture was stirred for 30 h and filtered off. Toluene was removed under reduced pressure and hexane was added to precipitate the ylide. The ylides were recrystallised from toluene-hexane.

Reaction of ylides with aromatic aldehydes: To a solution of the ylide (0.003 mol) in anhydrous toluene was added aromatic aldehyde (0.003 mol) and the mixture was heated at about 80° for 50 h. Toluene was then removed and the products were separated by column chromatography using alumina.

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A New Synthesis of Aroyl Cyanides from Phenacyl Bromides

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1-Amino-4,6-diphenyl-2-pyridene^{1,2} (1) and **1-amino-4,6-diphenyl-2-thioxo-1,2-dihydropyridine³ (2)** have been reported as reagents for the facile conversion of aldehydes into nitriles by pyrolysis of the aldimine intermediates. The work also has been extended⁴ for a convenient alternative synthesis of aromatic and aliphatic nitriles (6) from the aldehydes (4) via pyrolysis of aldimines (5) derived from 3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolines (3)

(Chart 1). The aldimines are readily prepared by the reaction of 3 with aromatic aldehydes and the reaction is completed at the boiling point of the solvent employed. The conversion 5→6+7, involves fission of the N-N bond and the process is facilitated by an intramolecular transfer in which the carbonyl group acts as an internal base.

Chart 1

We report herein a rapid and facile one-pot reaction for the conversion of phenacyl bromides into aroyl nitriles by the use of 2-aryl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-5(1H)-one (3) (where aryl R¹ = C₆H₅, C₆H₅CH₂) in DMSO. The reaction of 3 with phenacyl bromides in hot DMSO gave on subsequent workup the aroyl cyanides (9) in appreciable yields. The reaction presumably proceeds via the formation of aldimines (8) intermediate generated from 3 and the unstable arylglyoxal⁵ produced in the reaction medium. Under the reaction conditions, the aldimine (8) intermediate is pyrolysed to give a mixture of aroyl cyanide (9) and 4(3H)-quinazolinone (7) (Chart 2). The aroyl cyanide thus formed could be easily separated from the reaction mixture in hot benzene. The ir spectra of aroyl cyanides show strong intense peaks at 2230-2280 (C≡N) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

Chart 2

This method, thus, has got considerable synthetic importance in providing an alternate and convenient route for the synthesis of aroyl cyanides without the use of external cyanide ion. Further, the easy preparation of 2-aryl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolines (3) takes the advantage of replacing the 2-pyridone derivatives as reported earlier.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a WISWO melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

2-Phenyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3a; $R^1 = C_6H_5$) and 2-benzyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3b; $R^1 = C_6H_5CH_2$) were prepared following literature procedure^{6,7}.

Reaction of 2-phenyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3a) with phenacyl bromides. Isolation of aroyl cyanides (typical procedure): A solution of phenacyl bromide (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) in DMSO (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 20 h. The aminoquinazoline (3; 1.2 g, 0.005 mol) was then added and the mixture was heated for 6 h at 100°. It was then poured after cooling into ice-water (50 ml), extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml), dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated in vacuum. The crude product was treated with benzene when a solid settled which was filtered to give 7 ($R^1 = C_6H_5$), m.p. 234° (lit.⁶ 235°). The benzene filtrate on concentration in vacuum and subsequent trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave a low melting solid of benzoyl cyanide (0.8 g, 62%), m.p. 32° (lit.⁶ 32–5°).

In a similar manner, reaction of 3 with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide gave the corresponding *p*-methylbenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 49° (lit.¹⁰ 50–2°), *p*-chlorobenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 41° (lit.¹¹ 41.0–2.5°) and *p*-nitrobenzoyl cyanide, m.p. 115–16° (lit.¹² 116°) in 70, 72 and 54% yields, respectively.

Reaction of 2-benzyl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (3b) with phenacyl bromides. Isolation of aroyl cyanides: The preparative procedure adopted was the same as above. The benzene insoluble product in all cases was 7 ($R^1 = C_6H_5CH_2$), m.p. 255–56° (lit.⁶ 256°). The respective yields of aroyl cyanides isolated from the benzene-petroleum ether fractions were 58, 62, 65 and 50% in case of phenacyl bromide, *p*-methylphenacyl bromide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide and *p*-nitrophenacyl bromide.

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Synthesis of Novel Types of 1,4-Oxazino- and 1,4-Pyrazino-phenazine Derivatives

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LITERATURE survey showed that 1,4-benzoxazines are associated with a wide range of biological and pharmacological properties^{1–4}. Various derivatives of dihydropyrazines are reported to be potent antimalarial and antibacterial agents^{5–7}. Pyrazino[2,3-*b*]phenazine has been claimed to have potential action against leaf blast fungal disease⁸ in green-house. The condensed oxazines also possess fluorescent brightening property⁹. In continuation of our earlier work on fused heterocyclic systems^{10,11}, we describe here the synthesis and antibacterial and antifungal activities of the title compounds.

Various 2-aryl-(1,4)oxazino[5,6-*b*]phenazines (3) have been prepared by refluxing 2-amino-3-hydroxyphenazine^{1,2} (1) and phenacyl bromides (2) in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate. The above cyclisation in tetrahydrofuran gave low yields. The 2,3-diaminophenazine^{1,2} (4) was cyclised with phenacyl bromides (2) by refluxing them in dry acetone containing potassium carbonate to give 2-aryl-3,4-dihydro[1,4]pyrazino[5,6-*b*]phenazines (5).

All the compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data and a few have